

Complexes of the Metal Ion with *N*-Acylpeptides. Part-III. Preparation and Characterisation of Chromium(III) Complexes with *N*-Protected Dipeptides

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Complexes of the type $(Cr, I_3(OH)_2 \cdot xH_2O$ and $Cr_2I_6 \cdot xH_2O$ (LH-*N*-formyl, *N*-acetyl, monochloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-L-phenylalanyl-glycine and *N*-benzoyl-DL-alanyl-glycine; $x = 2-6$) have been prepared in ethanol and characterised on the basis of elemental, magnetic, conductance, ir, electronic and esr spectral data. The chromium(III) complexes are non-electrolytes. Carboxylate group coordinates in a bidentate manner. The results indicate an octahedral structure of the chromium(III) complexes.

RECENTLY the biochemistry of chromium has attracted a lot of interest due to its presence in the glucose tolerance factor (GTF) and its role in the enhancement of ribonucleic acid synthesis^{1,2}. The GTF is a mixture of chromium(III) nicotinic acid and the amino acids (glycine, glutamic acid and cysteine which stimulates the rate of carbon dioxide production in a yeast bioassay system³. It has been further reported that none of the *N*-coordinated complexes possess any glucose tolerance factor activity. Only *O*-coordinated complexes possess glucose tolerance factor activity⁴.

Neutral complexes of chromium with the following ligand combinations have been studied as model systems for chrome tanning: glycylglycine and glycine, glycylglycine and alanine, glycylalanine and glycine, glycylglycine and aspartic acid, and glycylaspartic acid and glycine. Electronic spectra of the complexes in aqueous solution indicated an octahedral environment around chromium(III). Infrared spectra of the complexes showed a considerable shift in the position of the absorption bands for carboxyl groups showing their involvement in bonding to chromium(III) ion. The ¹H nmr spectra contained broad bands whereas those of the ligands showed characteristic multiplets for CH, CH₂ and CH₃ groups. The broadening was attributed to the paramagnetic nature of the chromium(III) species⁵.

The main purpose of the present study is to evaluate the effects of substituents present directly on the amino group. These substituents diminish the affinity of the amino group for the metal ions and could permit a variety of coordination types.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analytical grade. All the five dipeptides were prepared in the laboratory. Purity of the dipeptides was checked by tlc.

The compounds were characterised by melting point determination and ¹H nmr spectra. The following *N*-acyldipeptides were prepared: *N*-formyl-L-phenylalanyl-glycine (For-Phe gly), *N*-benzoyl-DL-alanyl-glycine (Bz-Ala.gly), *N*-acetyl-L-phenylalanyl-glycine (Ac-Phe.gly), monochloroacetyl-L-phenylalanyl-glycine (MCA-Phe.gly) and trifluoroacetyl-L-phenylalanyl-glycine (TFA-Phe.gly).

L-Phenylalanine and DL-alanine (Sisco, India), trichloroacetic acid, chloroacetic acid, acetic anhydride, formic acid, benzoyl chloride, ethyl acetate, chloroform and benzene (all E. Merck) were used. All the dipeptides except Bz-Ala.gly were prepared by condensation of the corresponding protected amino acids and glycine ethyl ester using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide as a coupling reagent followed by hydrolysis; and in Bz-Ala gly preparation, EEDQ was used as a coupling reagent.

Tetra(N-acyldipeptidato)-μ-dihydroxodichromium(III) hydrates: A mixture of chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate (0.01 mol) and *N*-protected dipeptides (0.02 mol) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed over a water-bath for 0.5 h. After adding solid NaOH (0.03 mol) it was again refluxed for 6-7 h. The solution was then filtered while hot and concentrated to a semi-solid state. The resulting solid complex was washed with hot water and kept in a desiccator (H₂SO₄) for a few days. It was powdered and dried under reduced pressure at room temperature. The complexes with Ac-Phe.gly, MCA-Phe.gly and TFA-Phe.gly were prepared from chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate.

Hexa(N-acyldipeptidato)dichromium(III) hydrates: Chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate (0.01 mol) and *N*-acyldipeptides (0.031 mol) were dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and rest of the procedure followed was the same as above.

The molar conductance of the chromium(III) complexes was measured on a Toshniwal CLOI/02A conductivity bridge using a conventional dip type platinum electrode⁶. The magnetic moment of the powdered samples at room temperature was measured by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant⁷. The diamagnetic corrections for the ligands and the metal ion were applied using appropriate Pascal constant^{8,9}. ESR spectra were recorded at room temperature on a Jeol FE-3XG X-band instrument, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer. Elemental analysis was performed at the Regional Sophisticated and Instrumentation Centre, Chandigarh. Metal was estimated volumetrically by EDTA using eriochrome black-T as indicator.

Results and Discussion

Eight complexes of chromium(III) (prepared in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratio) were characterised by various physical and spectroscopic techniques. All the complexes were found to be stable in air having greyish or green colour and stable for a long time in a desiccator (CaCl₂). These are soluble in polar solvents like methanol, ethanol and acetone but insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene and ethyl acetate.

The chromium(III) complexes are non electrolytes in methanol (Table 1). The magnetic moments at room temperature are close to normal high-spin octahedral or slightly distorted chromium(III) complexes. The isotropic value of *g* (1.999–2.044) in esr spectrum shows an octahedral geometry of these complexes. In the electronic spectra, two main bands at 17 100–17 500 and 22 900–23 800 cm⁻¹ observed in ethanolic solution (Table 1) can be assigned to the transitions ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{2g} and ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g} (F) for octahedral chromium(III) complexes. The third spin-allowed transition *ν*₃ [⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g} (P)] is expected to occur at 35 000–38 000 cm⁻¹ but the charge transfer or ligand bands make its correct location impossible

The *ν*_{NH} band of the complexes are observed at slightly lower energy region (3 290–3 320 cm⁻¹) as compared to free dipeptides (3 300–3 400 cm⁻¹).

Shifting of the band to lower energy side may be due to hydrogen bonding with water or adjacent molecule. The NH bending mode in peptides mostly occurs at 1 540 cm⁻¹ but in the complexes it lies at the same or slightly lower region (1 530–1 545 cm⁻¹) which rules out coordination from the peptide nitrogen. The amide-I band observed at 1 610–1 660 cm⁻¹ in the ligands, shifted to higher frequency region (1 615–1 670 cm⁻¹) in the complexes which indicates weaker hydrogen bonding by CO group as compared to strong hydrogen bonding in *N*-acyldipeptides. This shows a non-coordinating behaviour of CO group. Two bands of medium intensity present at 2 520 and 2 720 cm⁻¹ due to *ν*_{OH} disappeared in the complexes indicating the coordination of carboxylate group to the metal ion. In order to decide about the coordination behaviour of carboxylate group, three criteria are used: (i) position of *ν*_s(OCO), (ii) separation between *ν*_s(OCO) and *ν*_a(OCO) i.e. Δ*ν* and (iii) direction of bond shift (DBS) of carboxylate antisymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies. These three criteria support the bidentate coordination of carboxylate group in the chromium(III) complexes. In the case of the OH bridge, the Cr–OH–Cr bond frequency lies at 550–590 cm⁻¹, because in an angular system, the asymmetric frequency decreases as a result of the weakening of the bridge bonding. In the infrared spectra of the complexes, no characteristic peaks of water could be identified at 3 200–3 550 and 1 600–1 630 cm⁻¹ for *ν*_s(OH) and δ(HOH) due to the presence of NH and C=O stretching frequencies. These peaks are merged with each other and broad bands appear indicating the presence of lattice water in the chromium(III) complexes.

Conclusion: The *g* value obtained for the chromium(III) complexes are very close to 2, indicating the absence of any appreciable orbital contribution to the moment. The magnetic moments of binuclear complexes are remarkably lower (3.01–3.68 B.M.) in comparison to the spin-only value (3.87 B.M.) which indicates an angular Cr–OH–Cr system in the dimers. An octahedral structure is proposed for the chromium(III) complexes with coordination from four oxygen atoms of two car-

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	<i>ν</i> ₃ ⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (F)	<i>ν</i> ₁ ⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g}	<i>g</i>	Molar conductance Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	<i>μ</i> _{eff} B.M.
1.	[Cr(For-Phe.gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	23 700	17 400	2.025	69	3.36 (311)
2.	[Cr(Bz-Ala.gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	23 000	17 200	2.044	20	3.01 (311)
3.	[Cr(Ac-Phe.gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	23 300	17 200	1.999	59	3.20 (307)
4.	[Cr(MCA-Phe.gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	23 400	17 200	2.038	59	3.68 (308)
5.	[Cr(TFA-Phe.gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	23 800	17 200	2.014	70	3.27 (308)
6.	[Cr(Ac-Phe.gly) ₂] ₃ .6H ₂ O	22 900	17 100	2.014	77	3.27 (307)
7.	[Cr(MCA-Phe.gly) ₂] ₃ .6H ₂ O	23 300	17 100	2.041	79	3.60 (308)
8.	[Cr(TFA-Phe.gly) ₂] ₃ .6H ₂ O	22 900	17 100	2.026	73	3.42 (308)

